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CLINICAL COURSE OF PEPTIC GASTRIC ULCER IN COMBINED WITH DIABETES TYPE 2**Ratsa V.,***Assistant Department of Internal Medicine Bukovinian State Medical University Chernivtsi, 58002***Bazhanska I.,***Doctor Regional Communal Noncommercial Enterprise Chernivtsi Regional Clinical***Semeniuk V.,***4th-year student of the 26th group at the BSMU in Chernivtsi, Ukraine***Yonyk V.,***4th-year student of the 26th group at the BSMU in Chernivtsi, Ukraine***Galchenko B.,***4th-year student of the 26th group at the BSMU in Chernivtsi, Ukraine***Buzdugan I.,***Candidate of Medical Sciences,**Assistant Department of Internal Medicine Bukovinian State Medical University**Chernivtsi, 58002*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7878642>**Abstract**

The article highlights the role of *Helicobacter pylori* strains in the course of peptic gastric ulcer in combination with diabetes type 2. The changes in the clinical picture, namely enhancement Opportunities of the body.

Keywords: peptic ulcer, diabetes type 2, clinic, *Helicobacter pylori*.

Actuality of theme. About 5 million patients with PVS are registered in Ukraine, with this disease occurred 2-3 times more often among the rural population among the urban population. However, diabetes mellitus type II (CD 2) is the first among diseases of endocrine pathology (occupies about 70% of all pathology) [1], the combination of these pathologies increases the risk of complications and mortality [2-4].

A certain group of pathogens in the peptic gastric ulcer associated with the rapid progression of atherosclerosis (AU), insulin resistance (IP) and hyperinsulinemia (GI) is identified. These include representatives of the Herpesviridae family (including CMV, HSV-1, EBV), *Chlamydia pneumoniae*, *Helicobacter pylori* (HP), *Porphyromonas gingivalis* [3]. The occurrence of endothelial damage due to the direct effect of *H. pylori* and stimulation of systemic and local inflammation is known [9]. At the same time, the ways of realization of *H. pylori* on the cardiovascular and endocrine systems are not fully understood [10].

The frequency of the joint course of PVS with AH and CD 2 smoothes the clinical manifestations of the underlying disease, so today the combination of such diseases is relevant.

Purpose: to evaluate the clinical course of peptic gastric ulcer combined with type 2 diabetes.

Materials and methods. Clinical examinations were performed 98 patients. Of these: 50 people suffer from PVS (group # 1), 48 people - PVS in combined with diabetes 2 (group # 2). The state of severity in all groups was mild and moderate.

The diagnosis of peptic ulcer of the stomach and duodenum and therapeutic tactics was established according to Order No. 271 of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine (dated 13.06.2005), diagnostic criteria age gradation of persons and a unified protocol "On approval and implementation of medical and technological documents on standardization of medical care in type 2 diabetes" Order of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine No. 1118 of 21.12.2012.

Criteria for inclusion in the study: male and female patients over 18 years of age with verified peptic gastric ulcer associated with toxigenic (CAGA, VACA) strains *H. pylori*, including combined with diabetes of 2 mild and moderate, sub-component.

Research results. It is known that the development of erosive changes in the SOS occurring on the eve of PVS formation is associated with the impact of HR strains having a combined virulent genotype CAGA and VACA. Further progression of the disease and the development of CO ulcer defects is accompanied by a change in the HR genotype, which can occur as a result of persistence of several HR strains in the same patient who has a high-volume gene of the gene in the genotype structure, and the combination of Hr CAGA and VACA genotypes. and development of ulcerative defects [3,6].

The dependence of the severity and compensation of CD 2 on the *Helicobacter pylori* genotypes is given in Table. 1.

Table 1

Dependence of CD 2 on the genotype (CAGA, VACA) of toxigenic strains of HR in examined patients, %

Disease		PG (n=30)	
		CagA+VacA+(n=13)	CagA+VacA- /CagA-VacA+(n=17)
Diabetes2(n=48)	Mild severity (n=20)	5 (38,46%)	9 (52,95%)
	Average severity (n=28)	8 (61,54%)	8 (47,05%)
	The compensation stage (n=22)	5 (38,46%)	10 (58,82%)
	Subcompensation Stage (n=26)	8 (61,54%)	7 (41,18%)

Assessing the prevalence of CD2, it was found that mild severity in the group of patients with PVS in the presence of toxigenic strains CAGA+ VACA+ occurs in 5 persons, and in the presence of CAGA+ VACA-/CAGA-VACA+ this disease occurs more often in patients with PVS (52.95%). The average severity of CD2 was found in 8 people with CAGA+ VACA+ PVS (61.54%), in 8 people CAGA+ VACA-/CAGA-VACA+ PVS

(60.71%). The stage of subcompensation was found to be more common in PVS patients, including CAGA+ VACA+ PVS 8 people (61.54%), with CAGA+ VACA-/CAGA-VACA+ PVS 7 people (41.18%).

The clinical course of PVS is accompanied by pain, dyspeptic and antenna-vegetative syndromes. The combination of PVS with diabetes 2 burdens the course of the underlying disease.

Pain syndrome was accompanied by epigastric and night pains. According to the examinations, epigastric pain syndrome is observed in 75% of patients with PVS, and in patients with PVS with hypertension and CD2 - in 80%, which indicates an increase in pain in patients with concomitant pathology.

Patients with PVS with CD2 are more likely to have pain in the epigastric region, which is 11.12% increased compared to patients with PVS. Night pains are more common in PVS patients (28.88% increase) and a decrease in pain after eating is increased in patients with PVS with CD2 (by 24.44%) compared to patients with PVS without TD2.

In turn, dyspeptic syndrome, manifested by complaints of nausea, belching of air, feeling of overflow and severity in the epigastric after eating, was observed in two groups of patients.

Dyspeptic syndrome is manifested in all patients, but increased in the group of patients with PVS with diabetes 2.

Astheno-vegetative syndrome was manifested by irritability, license, shortness of breath. Irritability was observed in 90% of patients with PVS with diabetes 2 and 43.33% of patients with PVS with concomitant pathology. Shortness of breath at exercise was observed in group # 2 - 76.66% and 56.66% - in group # 1 This relationship between the basic and concomitant pathology indicates the mutual intervention of these pathologies and the complication of the course of the main in the presence of concomitant pathology.

Conclusions. Patients with peptic gastric ulcer combined with type 2 diabetes have changes in the clinical picture, ie increased pain (epigastric pain (11.12%) and reduction of pain after Izhi (24.44%)), dyspeptic syndrome (nausea (nausea (nausea (nausea (nausea by 6.67%)), feeling overflow (by 21.66%) and severity in the stomach after eating (by 3.44%)) and asthenic-vege-

tative syndrome)) compared to patients with peptic gastric ulcer without concomitant pathology, which indicates an increase in the clinic in combination with concomitant pathology, a violation of the compensatory capacity of the body and is an important factor in the diagnosis of the disease.

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